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The effect of leadership style on employee motivation, case study: Al-Neelain University in Sudan -Khartoum)

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Abstract

At every level of the company, the efficacy of leadership is essential. In order to motivate, various firms adopt a range of leadership styles and techniques. By putting in place frameworks that maximize employee potential, utilize organizational resources, and provide guidance, leaders may inspire their workforce. On the other hand, they can make it extremely difficult to instill trust, buy into the company's goals, promote alignment, and create a collaborative environment. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between employee motivation and leadership style at Sudan's Al-Neelain University. The outcomes of the investigation were determined by the researcher using the quantitative approach. A questionnaire that was sent to administrative staff members at Al-Neelain University was used to collect the primary data. The statistical analysis, which was done using SPSS 22, revealed that motivation and leadership styles had a generally positive significance.

Keywords: Leadership; Motivation; Democratic leadership; Autocratic leadership; Laissez-Faire leadership

1. Introduction

The type of leadership a company adopts has a significant impact on whether or not it is successful in achieving its goals. It is believed that wise leadership plus a motivated workforce produce a lucrative and long-lasting business organization. (Löfsten, 2016). Organizations are essentially driven by people since they give their all to them and help them accomplish their objectives. (Gibson, 2011). Every company in the world was founded to fulfill one of two needs: to make a profit or to serve the community through social services, and in some circumstances, to fulfill both needs simultaneously. Thus, the corporate goals of all organizations are comparable. Businesses need employees to help them achieve their goals and objectives, but people also need inspiration and motivation from their leaders.

Retaining and motivating employees is the most important thing to do because their presence is the foundation of the firm (Mullins, 2007). Because improving a firm's performance requires good leadership, the success or failure of a corporation is determined by the efficacy of leadership at all levels of the organization. Leadership is the set of values, behaviors, and skills needed to persuade people to achieve organizational goals. (Shirzad,2011). Because of this, leadership can be characterized as a strategy for persuading others to work toward a common objective.

The behavior a person exhibits when attempting to affect how others perceive their actions is referred to as their leadership style. (Hersey,1988). Employee behavior is influenced by leadership inside the organization (Naile and Selesho, 2014). Successful leaders are the archetypal figures who shape the conduct of their subordinates and followers in order to accomplish the aims and objectives of the organization. The ideals, willingness to accept change, and motivation of employees can all be influenced by organizational leaders. (Michael,2010)

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Workplace motivation, on the other hand, is a challenging issue for any firm. Work motivation, as defined by (Luthan , 2006), is what keeps an individual inspired at work. (Luthan ,2006) claims that the process of motivation begins with the psychological or psychological efficiency that fuels the behaviors or impulses displayed for a specific purpose. According to (Robbins,2005), motivation is a persistent psychological process that initiates, directs, and maintains behavior. According to statistics, an engaged workforce produces superior organizational and employee performance as indicated by the accomplishment of the mission, the achievement of predetermined goals and objectives, efficiency, sustainability, bottom line, growth, and competitiveness (Nyberg et al., 2016). Establishing a motivational plan necessitates taking into account elements that motivate employees to perform at their highest level both individually and collectively, and as a result, leaders have an impact on employee effectiveness (Saad & Abbas, 2019).

In essence, driven people can complete any assignment, regardless of how small, challenging, or seemingly impossible it may seem. Employee motivation occurs at various levels and scales in the workplace depending on the cultural and leadership values observed by an organization, but it is debatable whether the approach used has an impact on employee commitment to their specific tasks, personal and organizational objectives, and team and their ultimate goals in a positive or negative way (Recklies, 2014).

Fundamentally, the key to developing a strategy for employee motivation is to understand what motivates each individual and each team. In relation to this, (Thoha ,2003) proposes that the leadership style of superior and authority leaders determines the motivation of employee work, however (Mangkunegara,2005) asserts that the motivation is shaped by the attitude (attitude) employees have toward work situations in the organization. The state or force known as motivation pushes the targeted employee or targeted employees to achieve the organization's goals. Therefore, employee motivation is crucial for the efficient operation of both businesses and employees. If employee motivation is poor, the employee will be lethargic to carry out tasks and obligations, and the results will not be what the organization expects.

This study provides evidence for the impact of leadership on employee motivation. The conceptual framework and research hypothesis are discussed at the beginning of the paper before the literature review. The research procedures, samples, and data analysis strategies are discussed after that. The study's findings are then discussed in order to address the posed hypothesis. The study's findings' conclusions and recommendations are then presented.

2. Leadership styles

Over the years, studies have highlighted many leadership approaches such as transformational, democratic, laissez-faire, paternalistic, authoritarian, and transactional styles. The differentiating component in these leadership mechanisms is decision making process. In autocratic surrounding, leaders do not allow junior employees to be involved in the decision making, employees' opinion and perspective are not taken into consideration in designing organization policies (Jogulu, 2010). According to (Harold and Holtz ,2015), in the situation demanding in depth involvement or great deal of pressure, strict adherence to stipulated procedure, or need for high quality outcome, the type of leadership style employed ensures the followers perform tasks required of them while avoiding making complex decisions. (Tuckey,2017) and (Samad, 2015) perceived the technique set in place platform where it allows group develop into highly skilled at performing assigned tasks and under stipulated rules for instance in military and construction industry. As illustrated by (Trivisonno and Barling 2016), the efficiency of the organizational activities emanates from the fact that one person is in charge of organizational operation that include setting roles, assigning task, and stipulating quality and time frame of the tasks. The two most prominent leadership approaches are transformational and authoritarian.

2.1. Autocratic leadership style

Autocratic leadership also referred to as authoritarian leadership is an approach where the leaders have full control over the decision-making process strategizing on organizational approaches including problem solving techniques and taking advantages of opportunities with little regard to advice and opinion from followers.

Autocratic leaders are asserting from strong authority and power over others. (Zenger and Folkman, 2002). Autocratic leaders wield enormous power and influence to manipulate others. Because they have authority over their followers, authoritarian leaders provide specific and concise instructions for completing tasks. Authoritarian leadership never allows workers to make decisions and keeps a distance from followers. They believe that to be a leader in person or a group, and one must keep a distance from the individuals (Egwunyenga, 2010). Many academics believe that most totalitarian regimes do not pay enough attention to socio-emotional aspects of organizations, such as group cohesion and the promotion of cohesiveness as a fundamental component in social life cycles (Yukl, 2014). According to (De Cremer ,2004) when there is no autocratic leadership, followers will feel attached to the group and coworkers.

Studies on the beneficial attributes of autocratic leadership have placed emphasis on time and convenience in decision making process. According to (Nanjunde and Swamy 2012), leaders can make a decision concerning an organization or a group without consulting or seeking approval from large group of people. In same argument, (Northouse ,2017) asserted that some decision requires strong leadership traits for approaches and things to be done efficiently and in timely manner. (Solaja, 2016) argued that if the leaders or manager is the most knowledgeable or experienced person in the group, the technique will ultimately lead to effective and fast decision-making process.

2.2. Democratic leadership style

Employees are considered when making decisions in this leadership style. Leaders with this leadership style offer options and assistance to their followers. Democratic leadership, also known as participatory leadership, stands for, as the name implies, fair participation, inclusion, and self-determination; however, it is not to be confused with individuals who hold elected positions of power (Igbaekemen and Odivwri, 2015). Accountability, active participation, collaboration, and delegation of duties and responsibilities are how democratic leaders establish authority. The democratic leadership's duties within the organization include distributing responsibilities and fostering group debates. Accepting personal responsibility for the organization, accountability for their choices, wanting to preserve their collective's self-determination and independence, taking on the role of leader when required or appropriate, and cooperating with leaders are all responsibilities of democratic followers (McShane et al., 2009).

2.3. Laissez-faire leadership

In this leadership style, leaders are not involved with their subordinates or followers. This style is characterized by the absence leadership style. Laissez-faire leaders do not make group-associated decisions and policies. Subordinates or followers are responsible for making all the decisions and solving problems. According to (Luthans, 2003), laissez-faire leadership is defined as the abdication of responsibilities and the refusal to participate in the motivational process. Laissez-faire leaders are uninterested in the efforts of their followers and coworkers. Leaders who employ a laissez-faire leadership style are frequently regarded as passive. Their attribution has a negative impact on their followers' performance (Judge and Piccolo, 2004). Laissez-faire leadership styles appear to be a passive type of leadership, according to (Hinkin and Schriesheim ,2008). Laissez-faire leaders do not have authority or have little authority within their organization. The major functions of this leadership style include trusting members to make appropriate decisions and hiring the trained employees. The role of this leadership style includes problem solving and self-monitoring along with producing quality products and services. Laissez-faire leaders are highly successful and their followers are self-directed as they are not critically instructed by their leaders at every step. This leadership style is suitable for organizations that have long-term employees. It is, however, not suitable for environments that require direction, quick feedback and praise (Uhl-Bien & Marion, 2009). The disadvantages of this style include lack of awareness, as it leads to poorly defined work roles. The leader provides minimal guidance, due to which group members are often not sure of their job roles and responsibilities.

2.4. Situational leadership style

Despite the fact that behavioral theories have been effective in proffering and articulating on leadership style choices, they have not provided any form of instruction regarding what constitutes effective leadership behaviors in a variety of situations (Bolden, 2004). Some scholars have come to the conclusion that no one leadership style is all-sufficient or right for every manager under every possible situation or circumstance. Consequently, situational theories were propounded to show that the style to be applied is largely dependent on the situation, the employees, the task at hand, the organization as well as other environmental factors. Although behavioral theories have helped propose and express potential leadership styles, they have failed to guide what constitutes effective leadership in various situations (Bolden, 2004). Some scholars believe that no single leadership style is all-encompassing or appropriate for every manager in every case or circumstance.

As a result, situational theories were developed to demonstrate that the appropriate style is heavily influenced by the circumstances, personnel, task at hand, organization, and other external factors. According to (Fielder ,1967), there is no such thing as a one-size-fits-all leadership strategy; instead, a thorough examination of the situation should be used to determine the leadership style. (Fielder, 1967) went on to differentiate between task-oriented managers and those who prioritize interpersonal relationships. Job-oriented managers, he claims, are more focused on the task at hand and perform better in situations where there is already a structure in place that promotes camaraderie or team spirit, defined duties, and either solid or weak leadership styles.

2.5. Dynamic leadership style

This is a dual-focused form of leadership style that is adaptive in nature. This leadership style changes and reacts to different situations. The theory of dynamic leadership holds that a leader should use a fluid style of leadership to adjust according to the team that is being led. Dynamic leadership helps improve team motivation, as dynamic leaders are characterized by effective action, focused energy and benevolent compassion. Further, dynamic leaders focus on engaging with employees in such a way that success is not based on any one individual, but the entire team. This particularly helps to motivate teams, as they experience a sense of recognition of their contribution to the overall success. Dynamic leaders are adaptive leaders, who find opportunities in obstacles, take effective action during difficult times and take risks (Pershing Yoakley & Associates, 2014). Dynamic leaders are appreciative of teams and the contribution of each employee; they are supportive of employees in different situations, are caring, fair, humble and inspiring. All these characteristics help a dynamic leader motivate teams rather than just individuals (Mostovicz, 2009). Dynamic leadership is an important resource for organizations that must operate in a highly competitive and dynamic business environment. Such leaders need to be both adaptive and flexible to operate according to the changing business environment (Wiesenthal et al., 2015).

2.6. Transformational leadership style

James MacGregor Burns was the pioneer of this concept of leadership. He defined transformational leadership as “a relationship of mutual stimulation and elevation that converts followers into leaders and may convert leaders into moral agents” (Burns, 1978). He further suggested that the concept occurs when “one or more persons engage with others in such a way that leaders and followers raise one another to higher levels of motivation and morality” (Burns, 1978). At the center of this perspective is a focus on the leaders’ ability to motivate and empower his/her followers along with the moral dimension of leadership. Burn’s idea later metamorphosed into what is today known as ‘transformational leadership’ where the leader transforms followers: “The objective of transformational leadership is to ‘transform’ people and organizations and to change them in mind and heart; enlarge their vision, insight, and understanding; clarify purposes; make behavior congruent with beliefs, principles, or values; and bring about changes that are permanent, self-perpetuating, and momentum building” (Bass and Jones, 2001). The approach has become popular with a variety of organizations and is used as a tool to bridge the gap created by organizational and human shortcomings as well as a way of coping with changing times.

2.7. Charismatic leadership styles

According to (Yukl, 2014), the word ‘charisma’ is derived from a Greek word which loosely translates to mean “divinely inspired gift”. The charisma of a leader is often displayed in situations of social crisis, where leaders emerge with radical visions, by offering creative solutions to their followers. Charisma is occasioned by a few behavioral differences unique to leaders and which the average individual does not possess. (Conger, 2009) describe charisma as a certain quality unique to a person which ultimately creates a charismatic leadership. In times of societal crisis, a leader’s charisma is typically demonstrated when they rise with bold ideas and offer imaginative solutions to their followers. Charisma is fueled by a set of personality traits that only leaders have, and the average person does not. According to (Conger, 2009), charisma is a distinct personality trait that leads to charismatic leadership. However, both the followers’ and the leader’s distinguishing characteristics can have an impact on a leader’s charismatic characteristics. (Willner, 2008) discovered that charismatic leadership is determined by perception rather than personality or environment. Simply put, it all comes down to how followers perceive their leader, not what the leader does to foster the charismatic bond. (Willner, 2008) went on to say that two factors influence the development of charisma in leaders and followers. It all comes down to the connection.

2.8. Transactional leadership style

The German philosopher, Max Weber was the pioneer of this concept of leadership style. He expounded it in his writing on the socio-economic style of organizations. He defined this leadership style as one that is earned through normative rules and regulations, control and discipline. This concept was introduced for the first time by Max Weber in his work on socio-economic considerations of the organization. In a similar fashion, (Burns, 2010) defined it as a work-related relationship that encourages a system of reciprocity, where a spirit of giving and take between manager and employee forms the basis of their official interactions. An example is a pay rise as a reward for commitment. The loyalty of employees was dependent on not just logic, but also on pre-existing contracts. Transactional leaders give priority to the aims and objectives of the organization and ensure that they are comprehensive and made crystal clear to employees. This type of leader is determined to overlook the private interest of his employees and does not create any room for sentiment. The style is clear and direct: “If you do this, you will get this”. Burns describes this kind of leadership as a “*favor-for-favor*” exchange, it is a trade-off of wants, a give and take so that all parties are satisfied that their objectives have been met. The style is particular on its insistence on carrying out set tasks in the proper way. The transactional

style of leadership consists of three major branches. They are (1) *Contingent Rewards* (2) *Management by Exception (passive)* and *Management by Exception (active)*.

3. Motivation

3.1. Meaning of motivation

Theoretically, employee motivation measures the commitment, creativity, and energy individuals bring into given tasks. Irrespective of organizational size or industry, employee motivation can have an incremental influence growth and performance of an organization. According to (Lazaroiu, 2015), lack of workforce motivation can be harmful causing such problems as complacency, disinterest, and widespread discouragement. Studies have demonstrated that employees perceive their contribution and performance in the form of long-term effect exert to an organization and making a difference. Taking into consideration individual views leading to positive results give a feeling of accomplishment and valuable (Yahaya, and Ebrahim, 2016). Motivation is an essential part of success and business prosperity in the existing dynamic and competitive market. It comprises of an individual's internal characteristics and the external factors that include job factors, individual differences and organizational practices (Gopal & Chowdhury, 2014). Motivation is the need for and expectation of work and the different factors in the workplace that facilitate team motivation (Bahmanabadi, 2015). It is important for managers to emerge as leaders so that they understand team members' needs and expectations, which drive the organization's culture. Of all the functions that a leader performs, motivating employees is the most important and complex task (Almansour, 2012). A major reason for this is that team motivation attributes change constantly. The major factors that motivate employees are fulfilling of needs, workplace justice, labor expended, employee development programs and policies of reward and appreciation (Hamidifar, 2009). Motivation is a process by which people participate in voluntary actions in the desired direction and stick to their goals and priorities (Ramlall, 2004). Motivation levels vary from person to person, and even within the same person, motivation levels might behave differently depending on the situation (Robbins, 2013). For this paper, motivation is operationally defined as the inner force that drives individuals to accomplish personal and organizational goals. Motivation concerns energy, direction, persistence and equifinality – all aspects of activation and intention and has been a central and perennial issue in the field of psychology, for it is at the core of biological, cognitive, and social regulation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Given today's economy, a motivated workforce represents both a competitive advantage and a critical strategic asset in any work environment (Trembley, 2009).

3.2. Motivation theories

Five major approaches that have led to our understanding of motivation are Maslow's need-hierarchy theory, Herzberg's two-factor theory, Vroom's expectancy theory, Adams' equity theory, and Skinner's reinforcement theory. According to Maslow, employees have five levels of needs (Maslow, 1943): physiological, safety, social, ego, and self-actualizing. Maslow argued that lower-level needs had to be satisfied before the next higher-level need would motivate employees. Herzberg's work categorized motivation into two factors: motivators and hygienes (Herzberg, Mausner, & Snyderman, 1959). Motivator or intrinsic factors, such as achievement and recognition, produce job satisfaction. Hygiene or extrinsic factors, such as pay and job security, produce job dissatisfaction. Vroom's theory is based on the belief that employee effort will lead to performance and performance will lead to rewards (Vroom, 1964). Rewards may be either positive or negative. The more positive the reward the more likely the employee will be highly motivated. Conversely, the more negative the reward the less likely the employee will be motivated. Adams' theory states that employees strive for equity between themselves and other workers.

Equity is achieved when the ratio of employee outcomes over inputs is equal to other employee outcomes over inputs (Adams, 1965). Skinner's theory simply states those employees' behaviors that lead to positive outcomes will be repeated and behaviors that lead to negative outcomes will not be repeated (Skinner, 1953). Managers should positively reinforce employee behaviors that lead to positive outcomes. Managers should negatively reinforce employee behavior that leads to negative outcomes.

3.2.1. Douglas McGregor theory X theory Y

Douglas McGregor (1960) was the first to propose the incentive theories X and Y. He identified two distinct forms of human nature. Managers believe that certain employees have a natural dislike of work and that monitoring and managing them in the workplace is crucial to the organization's performance, according to Theory X. Apart from hypothesis Y, ordinary people are willing to accept and even desire duties because they consider labor as a form of enjoyment and relaxation in the life of an organism.

Figure 1 Douglas McGregor’s model of motivation

3.2.2. Maslow's Need-Hierarchy Theory

Maslow's (1954) Hierarchy of Needs is one of the most well-known motivational variables in the world, according to (Haque,2014). According to Maslow's theory, "people continually seek something, and what they genuinely want depends on what they already have." Maslow categorized human needs into five categories: physiological, safety, love/belonging, esteem, and self-actualization. Maslow has organized these five criteria into layers from bottom to top: Workers' basic needs are at the bottom of the triangle. Addressing each of the bottom levels means the employee will be promoted to the next layer.

Figure 2 Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

3.2.3. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation

In 1959, Frederick Herzberg, a behavioral scientist proposed a two-factor theory or the motivator-hygiene theory. According to Herzberg, there are some job factors that result in satisfaction while there are other job factors that prevent dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg, the opposite of "Satisfaction" is "No satisfaction" and the opposite of "Dissatisfaction" is "No Dissatisfaction". (Robbins and Judge ,2013)

Figure 3 Herzberg’s view of satisfaction and dissatisfaction

Herzberg classified these job factors into two categories-**(Robbins and Judge, 2013)**.

3.2.3.1- Hygiene factors

Hygiene factors are those job factors which are essential for existence of motivation at workplace. These do not lead to positive satisfaction for long-term. But if these factors are absent/if these factors are non-existent at workplace, then they lead to dissatisfaction. Hygiene factors include: Pay: Company Policies and administrative policies: Fringe benefits: Physical Working conditions: Status: Interpersonal relations: Job Security

3.2.3.2- Motivational factors

According to Herzberg, the hygiene factors cannot be regarded as motivators. The motivational factors yield positive satisfaction. These factors are inherent to work. These factors motivate the employees for a superior performance. Motivational factors include: Recognition: Sense of achievement: Growth and promotional opportunities: Responsibility: Meaningfulness of the work:

Figure 4 Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory of Motivation

3.3. Relation between leadership and motivation

At the most basic level, leadership theories propose that leaders can have a powerful impact on individual, group, and organizational outcomes. Further, follower motivation is thought to be a primary mechanism through which leaders exert their influence. Thus, it follows that if leaders wish to improve outcomes, they should enhance the motivation of their followers (Harrell, 2008). Motivation is a goal-oriented characteristic that helps a person achieve his objectives. It pushes an individual to work hard at achieving his or her goals. A leader must have the right leadership traits to influence motivation. However, there is no specific blueprint for motivation (Locke and Latham, 1990). As a leader, one should keep an open perspective on human nature. Knowing different needs of subordinates will certainly make the decision-making process easier. (Orozi Sougui ,2017). Both an employee as well as manager must possess leadership and motivational traits. An effective leader must have a thorough knowledge of motivational factors for others.

The leader must understand the basic needs of employees Leadership is used as a means of motivating others.

The leaders can enhance the motivation of the employees by:

- Harmonize and match the subordinate needs with the organizational needs, the leader must ensure that the business has the same morals and ethics that he seeks in his employees.
- Appreciation and rewards-. Rewarding good/ exceptional behavior with a small token of appreciation, certificate or letter can be a great motivator.
- Being a role model -A leader should set a good example to ensure his people to grow and achieve their goals effectively.
- Encouraging individuals to get involved in planning and important issues resolution procedure not only motivates them, but also teaches the intricacies of these key decision-making factors.
- Developing moral and team spirit. -A leader's actions and decisions affect the morale of his subordinates. Hence, he should always be aware of his decisions and activities. Team spirit is the soul of the organization.
- step into the shoes of the subordinates - A leader should view things from subordinate's angle. He should empathize with them during difficult times. Empathizing with their personal problems makes them stronger-mentally and emotionally.
- The leader must make his employees feel they are performing an important work that is necessary for the organization's well-being and success. This motivational aspect drives them to fulfill goals.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Conceptual framework

This study investigates the perceived relationship between leadership styles and employee motivation levels at Nilein University. Specifically, the study investigates the relationship the three leadership styles (Authoritarian, Democratic and Laissez-Faire) have on motivation. Based on the literature review. The conceptual framework in this study is postulated as follows.

Figure 5 Conceptual Framework

4.2. Research problem and justification

In many African countries, statistics and reports show a rising trend of leadership incompetence, particularly in higher education institutions, and it is on the basis of these reports that this research attempts to investigate the impact of leadership style on employee performance.

4.3. Research objectives

The objectives of this study are:

- To experiment the effect of Authoritarian leadership style on employee motivation.
- To ascertain the impact of Democratic leadership style on employee motivation
- To investigate the effect of Laissez-faire leadership style on employee motivation
- To examine the relationship between leadership styles and employee motivation at Al-Neelain University

4.4. Research questions

This research will try to find an answer to the following questions:

- What are the effects of Authoritarian leadership style on employee motivation.
- What are the impacts of Democratic leadership style on employee motivation
- What are the effects of Laissez-faire leadership style on employee motivation
- How do the different leadership styles impact on the level of motivation of employees in at Al-Neelain University?

4.5. Research hypothesis

In light of the research problem and after analyzing the historical data related to leadership and motivation the researcher formulates the following hypotheses and their relationship are illustrated in Figure 1.

- H1: Authoritarian leadership style enhances employee motivation.
- H2: Democratic leadership style enhances employee motivation
- H3: Laissez-faire leadership style enhances employee motivation
- H4: There exists a relationship between leadership styles and employee motivation at Al-Neelain University

Figure 6 Hypotheses on the effects of leadership style on employee motivation

4.6. Research methodology

This research adopts the quantitative approach using the path analysis technique, that aims to analyze the influence of exogenous variables, namely leadership styles (**X1**) to endogenous variable, i.e., employee motivation (**Y**). The quantitative analysis was based on the survey data. To complete the study task effectively, the researcher conducted both primary and secondary research. Firstly, Secondary research was carried out by reviewing current and relevant literature related to leadership and motivation. A questionnaire to **60** employees from a general population of **120** employees who work in different administrative departments at Al-Neelain University was distributed to randomly selected employees. Respondents were asked to fill out and respond to the questionnaire given by giving a checklist to one of the alternative answers. The answers to each question item used a 5-point Likert scale (**1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree**). Overall, **60** valid questionnaires were received back and used in the research statistical analysis.

4.7. Validity and reliability test

The reliability analysis was performed to check the internal consistency of the participant responses, and the researcher used the Cronbach's Alpha method to test the internal consistency. The Alpha test results showed an Alpha value of **0.76**, more significant than the required value of **0.50**, indicating that the data collected for this study was internally consistent.

4.8. Correlation

The researcher used correlation and regression analysis to determine the relationship between different leadership styles and employee motivation. In the correlation analysis, employee motivation was used as the dependent variable, and leadership styles were used as the independent variables.

5. Result and Discussion

The authoritarian style of leadership had a negative effect on staff motivation. In terms of the autocratic leadership style, most of the participants agreed with the statements. Based on the responses, the results indicated that autocratic leaders used their great authority and power to exert control over others. Authoritarian leaders wield authority over their followers, they give precise and concise instructions for completing duties, and authoritarian leadership never allows workers to make choices and keeps a distance from followers. According to the study's findings, there was a strong positive connection between democratic leadership and employee motivation. In terms of the Democratic Leadership Style, there was a positive relation i.e., most of the participants agreed with the assertions that Employees are considered when making decisions; democratic leadership represents equitable involvement, inclusion, and self-determination, as the name implies, and democratic leadership practices are much more motivating than the other styles. In terms of the Laissez-faire Leadership Style there was a negative relation, most of the participants in this study agreed with the claims that, laissez-faire leadership was an abandonment of duties and a refusal to participate in the motivational process. Laissez-faire leaders are uninvolved in the work of their followers and coworkers, and laissez-faire leadership styles appear to be a passive type of leadership.

The statistical findings clearly indicate that the leadership styles all together have an effect on the enhancement of motivation level of the employees. This proves the fourth hypothesis (**H4**) which states that leadership styles have an overall effect on the motivation level of the employees. From this hypothesis, we can draw an inference that if the managers in the university are able to follow the leadership styles as given in the theory and are seen in the practice, they can help increase the motivation level of their employees. The first hypothesis (**H1**) that stated the authoritarian leadership style enhances employee motivation is insignificant, and hence it was rejected because its significance level was not within the prescribed limits. The second hypothesis (**H2**) which stated that democratic leadership style help enhanced employee motivation prove true as their relationship has been found significant and their unique effects had been observed. The third hypothesis (**H3**) which stated the Laissez-faire leadership style enhances employee motivation was found to have weak relationship with the motivation level because its significance level was not also within the prescribed limits.

6. Conclusion

Workplaces benefit greatly from having motivated staff. primarily because it enables management to accomplish the objectives of the business. Companies could be in a very perilous position without a motivated workplace. An organization can attain better levels of output with the help of motivated personnel who are more productive. An organization's success is correlated with its ability to motivate its workforce. Motivation is a non-tangible quality that is challenging to quantify and even more so to manage, yet it is remarkably simple to enable in a setting where democratic leadership is used.

Compliance with ethical standards

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References

- [1] Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequity in Social Exchange. In L. Berkowitz, *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*. New York: Academic Press.

- [2] Almansour, Y.M. (2012). The relationship between leadership styles and motivation of managers conceptual framework. *Journal of Arts, Science, and Commerce*, 3(1), 161-166.
- [3] Bahmanabadi, S. (2015). A Case Study of the Impact of Leadership Styles on Bank Employees' Job Satisfaction. Unpublished Bachelor's thesis, Södertörn university, Huddinge, Sweden.
- [4] Bass, Jones. (2001). *Bass and Stogdill's Handbook of Leadership* 3 edition free press
- [5] Bolden, R. (2004). *What is Leadership?* 1st ed. Exeter: University of Exeter. 59
- [6] Burns, A. (2010). *Doing Action Research in Language Teaching: A Guide for Practitioners*. NY: Routledge.
- [7] Burns, J.P. (2010). Complexity science and leadership in healthcare. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 31(10), 474-48.
- [8] De Cremer, D. (2004). The influence of accuracy as a function of leader's bias: The role of trustworthiness in the psychology of procedural justice. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 30, 293 – 304
- [9] Egwunyenga, E.J. (2010). *Essentials of school administration*. Benin City: Justice- Jeco Publishers.
- [10] Fiedler, F.E. (1967). *A Theory of Leadership Effectiveness*. Mc Graw-Hill Book Company, New York
- [11] Gibson, R. (2011). *Rethinking the future: rethinking business, principles, competition, control & complexity, leadership, markets and the world*. Hachette UK.
- [12] Gopal, R. & Chowdhury, R.G. (2014). Leadership styles and employee motivation: An empirical investigation in a leading oil company. *International Journal of Research in Business Management*, 2(5), 1-10.
- [13] Hamidifar F. (2009). *A Study of the Relationship between Leadership Styles and Employee Job Satisfaction at Islamic Azad University Branches in Tehran*. Tehran: Iran.
- [14] Haque, M., Haque, M. And Islam, M. (2014). *ASA University Review. Motivational Theories – A Critical Analysis*, 08(01), pp.62-68.
- [15] Harold, C. M., & Holtz, B. C. (2015). The effects of passive leadership on workplace incivility. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 36(1), 16-38.
- [16] Harrell, M. M. (2008). *The Relationships Between Leader Behavior, Follower Motivation, and Performance*. Florida: Department of Psychology College of Sciences University of Central Florida.
- [17] Hersey, Poni, & Ken Blanchard. (1988). *Manajemen Perilaku Organisasi, Pendayagunaan Sumber Daya Manusia Edisi Bahasa Indonesia*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [18] Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. B. (1959). *The Motivation To Work*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [19] Hinkin, T. And Schriesheim, C. (2008). A theoretical and empirical examination of the transactional and non-leadership dimensions of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ). *The Leadership Quarterly*, 19(5), pp.501-513.
- [20] Jogulu, U. D. (2010). Culturally-linked leadership styles. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 31(8), 705-719.
- [21] Judge, T.A. and Piccolo, R.F., (2004). Transformational and transactional leadership: a meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Journal of applied psychology*, 89(5), p.755
- [22] Lazaroiu, G., 2015. Employee motivation and job performance. *Linguistic and Philosophical Investigations*, 14, p.97.
- [23] Löfsten, H. (2016). New technology-based firms and their survival: The importance of business networks, and entrepreneurial business behaviour and competition. *Local Economy*, 31(3), 393-409.
- [24] Luthan, F. (2003). *Organization Behaviour (Alih bahasa Nurdin Sobali)*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [25] Mangkunegara. A.A. Anwar Prabu. (2005). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung : Remaja Rosdakarya
- [26] Maslow, A. H. (1943). A Theory of Human Motivation. *Psychological Review*, 370-396.
- [27] Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York: Harper and Row.
- [28] Michael. A. (2010). *Leadership style and organisational impact*.

- [29] Mostovicz, I. (2009). A Dynamic theory of leadership development. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 30(6), 563-76.
- [30] Mullins, A. (2007). *Management and Organisational Behavior*. 8th Edition. England: Pearson Education Limited.
- [31] Naile, I. And Selesho, J. (2014). The Role of Leadership in Employee Motivation. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5 (3), 175- 182.
- [32] Northouse, P. G. (2017). *Introduction to leadership: Concepts and practice*. Sage Publications.
- [33] Nyberg, A. J., Pieper, J. R., & Trevor, C. O. (2016). Pay-for-performance's effect on future employee performance: Integrating psychological and economic principles toward a contingency perspective. *Journal of Management*, 42(7), 1753-1783.
- [34] Pershing, Yoakley & Associates (2014). *Dynamic Leadership for Dynamic Times*. Pershing Yoakley and Associates.
- [35] Ramlall, S., (2004). A review of employee motivation theories and their implications for employee retention within organisations. *Journal of American Academy of Business*, 5(1/2), pp.52-63.
- [36] Recklies, D. (2014). Motivation - Basic Concepts and Theories. [online] *The manager.org*. Available at: <https://www.themanager.org/2014/12/motivation-basic-concepts-and-theories>
- [37] Robbins, S. And Judge, T. (2013). *Organisational behaviour*. 15th ed. New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [38] Robbins, Stephen P, Mary Coulter, 2005, *Management*, Volume 2, Issue 7, PT. Gramedia Index Group, Jakarta.
- [39] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self Determination Theory and The Facilitation of Interinsic Motivation, Social Developmen, and Well Being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68-78.
- [40] Saad, G. B., & Abbas, M. (2018). The impact of organizational culture on job performance: a study of Saudi Arabian public sector work culture. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 16(3), 207-218.
- [41] Samad, A., Reaburn, P., Davis, H., & Ahmed, E. (2015). An empirical study on the effect of leadership styles on employee wellbeing and organizational outcomes within an Australian regional university. In *Australasian Conference on Business and Social Sciences*, Sydney, Australia, April (pp. 13-14).
- [42] Solaja, M. O., Idowu, E. F., & James, E. A. (2016). Exploring the relationship between leadership communication style, personality trait, and organizational productivity. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 11(1), 99-117.
- [43] Thoah. Miftah. (2003). *Kepemimpinan Dalam Manajemen (cetakan 17)*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada
- [44] Trembley, M. A., Blanchard, C. M., Taylor, S., Pelletier, L. G., & Villeneuve, M. (2009). Work Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation Scale: Its Value for Organizational Psychology Research. *Canadian Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 41, 213-226.
- [45] Trivisonno, M. And Barling, J., (2016). 22. Organizational leadership and employee commitment. *Handbook of employee commitment*, 305.
- [46] Tuckey, M.R., Li, Y. And Chen, P.Y. (2017). The role of transformational leadership in workplace bullying: Interactions with leaders' and followers' job characteristics in a multi-level study. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, 4(3), 199-217.
- [47] Uhl-Bien, M., Marion, R. & mckelvey, B. (2007). Complexity leadership theory: Shifting leadership from the industrial age to the knowledge era. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 18(4), 298-318.
- [48] Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and Motivation*. New York: Wiley.
- [49] Wiesenthal, A.M., Kalpna, J., mcdowell, T. & Radin, J. (2015). The new physician leaders: Leadership for a dynamic health. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 1-3. Available at: [HYPERLINK](#)
- [50] Yahaya, R. And Ebrahim, F., (2016). Leadership styles and organizational commitment: literature review. *Journal of Management Development*, 35(2), 190-216.
- [51] Yukl, G. (2014). *Leadership in Organisations (7th Suppl.)*, Noida: Pearson India Education Services Pvt Ltd.
- [52] Yukl, G. A. (2002). *Leadership In Organizations*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [53] Zenger, John J., and Joseph Folkman (2002).